

Two new species of the genus *Calamia* Hübner, 1821 from India and Pakistan (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae, Apameini)

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Abstract. Two new species, *Calamia* (*Scotocalamia*) *fuscokeylongi* sp. n. and *Calamia* (*Scotocalamia*) *albomaculosus* sp. n. are described from India and Pakistan. The main external and genitalia diagnostic features of the new species and their closest relatives are characterised and discussed and illustrated with six colour figures, while the genitalia are presented with six monochromatic figures.

Keywords. *Calamia*, *Scotocalamia*, new species, description, taxonomy.

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Introduction

Varga et al. (2022) clarified the taxonomic problems related to the species "*Polia*" *scotochlora* Kollar, 1849 and established the new subgenus *Scotocalamia* for two taxa (*Calamia scotochlora* and *Calamia tshava* Hreblay & Ronkay, 1999), which were classified in the previously known genus *Calamia* Hübner, 1821. Additionally, they described *Calamia* (*Scotocalamia*) *sarahaadainae* Varga et al., 2022 as a new species in the subgenus and revised the status of *Sidemia stoliczcae tshava* Hreblay & Ronkay, 1999 (*Esperiana* 7: 557) as a new combination.

The author of this article studied the material of this subgenus and managed to find two species new to science, collected by Balázs Nagy during a non-lepidopterological travel to India, Himachal Pradesh in 1991, and by Vladimir Gurko during his 2005 expedition in the western region of Pakistan. Although these two new species well differ from the known three species of *Calamia* (*Scotocalamia*) in external features, the genitalia characters strictly indicate their association to *Calamia* (*Scotocalamia*).

There are two errors in the original description of the species *C. (Sc.) tshava* (Hreblay & Ronkay, 1999) (*Esperiana* 7, page 557; gen. fig. 606/161; colour photo Tafel XX/137). The holotype is depicted in reflection, probably because the describer reproduced the figures on colour slides, and the slide image was placed upside down in the copier. Later, it was correctly figured by Bálint et al. (2014) then Varga et al. (2022). In the original description, the slide number of the holotype is Hreblay 9904, however in reality, the gen. fig. 606/161 shows the Hreblay 9905, which is the slide number of the male paratype. Here the author figures the real holotype genitalia (Hreblay no. 9904) as well as that of the male paratype (Hreblay no. 9905).

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein are as follows: MH in HNHM = collection of Márton Hreblay in Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, Hungary); PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary). Other abbreviations used: GYP = genitalia slide prepared by Péter Gyulai; HM = genitalia slide prepared by Márton Hreblay; m = male; HT = holotype; PT = paratype.

Descriptions of new taxa

Calamia (Scotocalamia) fuscokeylongi sp. n. (Figs 3, 4, 9)

Holotype. male (Fig. 3), India, 3300 m, Himachal Pradesh, Keylong, Lahoul, 19. VIII. 1991, leg. B. Nagy, GYP 6223 (coll. PGM).

Paratype. male, with the same data, GYP 534 (coll. PGM).

Diagnosis. *Calamia (Scotocalamia) fuscokeylongi* sp. n. (Figs 3, 4) can be distinguished from all the other species of *Scotocalamia* (Figs 1, 2, 5, 6) by the variegated fuscous-greyish forewings and hindwings, particularly from the almost concolorous brown suffused *C. (S.) scotochlora* and *C. (Sc.) sarahsaadainae* and the much lighter, almost unicolorous, with slight olive suffusion and obscure wing patterned *C. (Sc.) tshava* (Hreblay & Ronkay, 1999). Additionally, its reniform stigmata are much larger, longer and the crosslines significantly more conspicuous and more whitish shaded than in *C. (S.) scotochlora* Kollar, 1849 and *C. (Sc.) tshava*.

In the male genital structure, *C. (Sc.) fuscokeylongi* sp. n. (Fig. 9) differs from *C. (S.) scotochlora* (Fig. 7) by the slightly longer but narrower uncus, the medially remarkably less broader valvae on the ventral side, longer, weaker aedeagus and shorter carinal thorn and cornutus plate of vesica; from those of *C. (Sc.) sarahsaadainae* (Fig. 8) by the somewhat broader but apically shorter uncus, more dorsally curved cucullus section, longer, weaker aedeagus with slightly shorter carinal thorn and wedge shaped cornutus plate of the less ample vesica; from those of *C. (Sc.) tshava* (Figs 11, 12) by the apically shorter uncus, triangular juxta, dorsally less elongate cucullus, longer, conspicuously weaker aedeagus and smaller carinal thorn and vesica.

The female is unknown.

Description (Figs 3, 4). Wingspan 37–40 mm. Antennae filiform, light greyish, with dense, pale yellowish, tiny cilia. Vesture of the head and thorax dark ash-greyish; that of the abdomen lighter. Forewing ground colour and the cilia dark ash-greyish with slight brown suffusion, the medial and terminal area and the subapical patch the darkest, while the subterminal area the lightest. Wing pattern mostly well-defined; crosslines blackish, the basal- and antemedial lines oblique, almost parallel, sinuous-zigzag, with fine white shade in the inner side; medial line diffuse, broad, dark brown; postmedial line strongly arcuated, lanced with fine white shade in the outer side of the lower section. The subterminal line sinuous, whitish, with a few fine brown triangles on the inner side; the terminal line fine, marked with tiny, scattered dark brown triangles. The orbicular and the reniform stigmata are conspicuous and typical; the orbicular macules are somewhat elongate, both of them with slight greyish suffusion, partly bordered with fine white. The hindwing pale brownish, with broad, darker and darker marginal area, and the veins with a darker brown tinge. Cilia pale brown. The underside of the wing is shiny, pale greyish-brownish suffused, all the wings with the obscure ghost of the upperside wing pattern.

Male genitalia (Fig 9). The uncus is lanceolate, apically obtuse. The valvae elongate, with a slight elongate depression submedially and without medial extension on the ventral side. The claw-shaped harpe-ampulla complex is flattened, terminally curved, apically pointed, and covering a long section of the dorsal costa. The cucullus „neck“ elongate, the cucullus asymmetrically elongate triangle-like, extended on the dorsal side, corona weak. The juxta triangular, the vinculum U-shaped. The aedeagus is curved, long, armed by a strong mediolateral thorn, and sitting on a long and strong sclerotized base. The vesica is rather long, semiglobular and recurved dorsal, possessing a small wedge-like, asymmetrically dentate, sclerotised plate in the distal curve of vesica, having two tiny apical teeth.

Etymology. The name of the new species is constructed from the dark colour and the name of the type locality.

Distribution. The new species is known from India, Himachal Pradesh.

***Calamia (Scotocalamia) albomaculosus* sp. n.** (Figs 5, 10)

Holotype. male, (Fig. 5), Pakistan, NWFP S. Waziristan agency, near Tanai vill., 28. VII. – 12. VIII. 2005, 1500 – 2500 m., leg. V. Gurko, slide no. GYP 6218 (coll. PGM).

Diagnosis. *Calamia (Scotocalamia) albomaculosus* sp. n. (Fig. 5) well differs from all its four subcongeners (Figs 1, 2, 3, 4, 6) by the smaller size, the less elongated forewing apex, the much more variegated, contrasty, and the lightest ground-coloured forewings, the pale greyish-brownish suffused basal-, subterminal- and terminal fields and the whitish reniform spots. The geographical distribution patterns differ, with the new taxon being the westernmost known species of the subgenus.

In the male genitalia capsule, *C. (Sc.) albomaculosus* sp. n. (Fig. 10) has the most diverging valvae, particularly in the cucullus section. It has more pointed uncus; not broadened, almost straight valval ventral edge; larger, on the dorsal side more elongated cucullus and smaller carinal thorn and cornutus plate of the vesica than in *C. (Sc.) scotochlora* (Fig. 7). The new species has broader uncus, larger, on the dorsal side straighter cucullus, while it is more broaden on the ventral side; dorsally broader juxta, slightly longer carinal thorn and broader cornutus plate of the distally wider vesica than in *C. (Sc.) sarahsaadainae* (Fig. 8). *C. (Sc.) albomaculosus* sp. n. differs from *C. (Sc.) tshava* (Figs 11, 12), straighter cucullus on the dorsal side, while it is more broaden, larger on the ventral side; dorsally more prominent juxta and shorter, much smaller cornutus plate of vesica; while those from *C. (Sc.) fuscokeylongi* sp. n. (Fig. 9), the new species has remarkably broader uncus and diverging valvae with larger, ventrally much extended cucullus; slightly longer carinal thorn and broader cornutus plate of the distally significantly wider vesica.

The female is unknown.

Description. (Fig. 5). Wingspan 34 mm. Antennae filiform, light greyish, with scattered tiny cilia. Vesture of the head and thorax dark brownish; that of the abdomen lighter. Forewing ground colour is very light greyish brownish, the medial and the costal area and the subapical patch the darkest, with more brown suffusion. Wing pattern mostly well-defined; crosslines brown, the antemedial line sinuous zigzag, with fine white shade in the inner side; medial line diffuse, broad, dark brown; postmedial line arcuated, lanced with fine white shade in the outer side; subterminal line sinuous, whitish, with a few fine brown triangles on the inner side; terminal line marked with tiny, scattered dark brown triangles. The orbicular and the reniform stigmata angular, whitish, the former one with slight greyish suffusion, the latter one conspicuous. Cilia are white with brown edges. Hindwing pale brownish whitish, with fine sinuous medial line; the marginal area broadly darker brown, the veins with a darker brown tinge. Cilia whitish with fine, pale brown sections. The underside of the forewings is pale greyish brownish, the marginal field and the hindwings whitish, all the wings with the obscure ghost of the main wing pattern on the upper side.

Male genitalia (Fig 10). The uncus is broadly lanceolate. The valvae elongate, without medial extension on the ventral side, with flattened claw-shaped harpe-ampulla complex, covering a long section of the dorsal costa. The cucullus „neck“ elongate, the cucullus asymmetrically elongate triangle-like, almost straight on the dorsal side, extended on the ventral side, corona weak. The juxta rhomboidal. The aedeagus is curved, armed by a strong mediolateral thorn, and sitting on a long and strong sclerotized base. The vesica is rather short, semiglobular and recurved dorsad, possessing a small stick-like, asymmetrically dentate, sclerotised plate in the distal curve of the vesica.

Etymology. The name of the new species is after its conspicuous whitish reniform stigmata of the forewings.

Distribution. The new species is known from Pakistan, Waziristan.

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Figures 1-6. *Calamia (Scotocalamia)* spp. adults. **1.** *C. (Sc.) scotochlora* Kollar, 1849, Pakistan, Himalaya, Kaghan v., leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); **2.** *C. (Sc.) sarahsaadainae* Varga et al., 2022, PT, Pakistan, Karakoram, GYP 5425, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); **3.** *C. (Sc.) fuscokeylongi* **sp. n.**, HT, India, Himachal Pradesh, Lahoul, Keylong, GYP 6223, leg. B. Nagy (PGM); **4.** *C. (Sc.) fuscokeylongi* **sp. n.**, PT, India, Himachal Pradesh, Lahoul, Keylong, leg. B. Nagy, GYP 534 (PGM); **5.** *C. (Sc.) albomaculosus* **sp. n.**, HT, Pakistan, NWFP S. Waziristan agency, GYP 6218, leg. V. Gurko (PGM); **6.** *C. (Sc.) tshava* (Hreblay & Ronkay, 1999), HT, Nepal, Annapurna Himal, HM 9904 (MH, in HNHM).

Figures 7-10. *Calamia (Scotocalamia)* spp. male genitalia. **7.** *C. (Sc.) scotochlora* Kollar, 1849, Pakistan, Himalaya, Ayubia, GYP 5423, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); **8.** *C. (Sc.) sarahsaadainae* Varga et al., 2022, PT, Pakistan, Hindukush, GYP 5428, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); **9.** *C. (Sc.) fuscokeylongi* **sp. n.**, HT, India, Himachal Pradesh, Keylong, GYP 6223, leg. B. Nagy (PGM); **10.** *C. (Sc.) albomaculosus* **sp. n.**, HT, Pakistan, NWFP S. Waziristan agency, GYP 6218, leg. V. Gurko (PGM).

Figures 11-12. *Calamia (Scotocalamia)* spp. male genitalia. **11.** *C. (Sc.) tshava* (Hreblay & Ronkay, 1999), HT, Nepal, Annapurna Himal HM 9904 (MH, in HNHM); **12.** *C. (Sc.) tshava* (Hreblay & Ronkay, 1999), PT, Nepal, Annapurna Himal HM 9905 (MH, in HNHM).